

Organic Farming and Its Implications for the Stakeholders

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Abstract

India has been a conspicuous player in the organics space. The organic agriculture space and the value of the products it accounts for have been clocking a healthy pace of growth. Awareness about organic products has been rising leading more and more farmers to go organic, so to speak. But with accreditation agencies having been conspicuous by their absence (until recently), producers and marketers with dubious credentials queered the pitch for the rest. Thus, the Indian organics marketers were in the news for all the wrong reasons. However, on Jan 1, 2019 the government of India mandated clear and legible consumer-friendly labeling for organic products. Hopefully, the flip side of the marketing practices associated with organic farm products will be addressed sooner rather than later, as a result. On interaction with organic farmers and experts on organic farming, the researcher concludes that post Jan 1, 2019 export of organic products to markets like US will improve. Organic farming will improve. In the medium term, the organics market will transition into a mainstream or mass market, given the country’s huge chunk of arable land. Customer base will widen.

Keywords: Accreditation, arable, mass market, niche market, organics, transition.

Statement of the Problem

Until marking requirements came into force on Jan 1, 2019 many undesirable and unhealthy practices characterised the organics space. Sections of various stakeholder categories were to blame for the plight. With the labelling requirements coming into force, it is hoped that such malpractices will cease, and the organics space will turn over a new leaf in the interest of the welfare of all its stakeholders.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are to:

1. Identify the flip side of the marketing practices associated with organic farm products in the country.
2. Analyse the implications of the mandate for the stakeholders associated with the organics industry

Hypothesis of the Study

H0: “Under the umbrella of organic products, non-organic products are not marketed”

H1: “Under the umbrella of organic products, some non-organic products are also marketed”.

Research Methodology

The study has been used the interview schedules for the purpose of collection of primary data. The study has been used both the primary and secondary data. Primary data has been collected from respondents and the respondents are farmers who are practicing organic farming. The secondary data has collected from the various official websites, books, journals, magazines, reports and other sources. In addition, the researcher interacted with other stakeholders like seed suppliers, pesticide and fertiliser manufacturers, food wholesalers, food standards agencies, occupational health and safety agencies, environmental regulatory agencies, animal welfare groups, rural residents and experts like toxicologists and epidemiologists on the subject. The study selected 50 organic farmers and experts operating in the area covered by the study at least for the past five years. Chi Squared test was used to analyse the data.

Flip Side of the Marketing Practices Associated with Organic Farm Products

Farm products are being marketed in the country in a way that is not exactly customer-friendly. Hence the researcher requested the respondents to disclose the flip side of the marketing practices associated with organic farm products in the country. Their answers to the question look as if in the following Table.

Table-1 Flip Side of the Marketing Practices Associated with Organic Farm Products

Flip side aspects	Number of respondents
Accreditation that establishes the “organic” content and nature of the product is not carried by the product	43
Under the umbrella of organic products, some non-organic products are also marketed	41
The prefix “organic” attracts a premium and hence some marketers and organic farmers game the system	39

Form the table-1 it is evident that, 43 respondents are agreed that, the content of organic which is established not carried the nature of the product. 41 respondents are responded that, the products which are not organic are also marketed in the name of organic products under the umbrella of the products of organic. As responded by 39 respondents it can be evident that, the name of organic has been attracting the farmers and marketers and are playing significant role in the system of market.

Implications of the New Organic Standards Mandated by the Regulator

On 1 January 2019, the government mandated clear and legible consumer-friendly labelling for organic products. Henceforth the study sought to know the inferences of the obligation for the stakeholders related with the organics industry. Their responses to the enquiry look in the following Table-2.

Table-2 Implications of the New Organic Standards Mandated by the Regulator

Implications	Number of Respondents
Transparent labelling will help rope in more farmers and more customers	40
Customer base will widen	38
Export of organic products to markets like US will improve	38
Organic farming will gain momentum	34

The table-2 indicates that, 40 respondents are accepted that, the large numbers of farmers and customers can certainly get the help of the transparent labeling of organic. And it is also earmarked that the base of the customers can be widened in the market as 38 respondents are expressed. As United States it can be helped the products to export to the other countries in the name of organic products as responded by 38 respondents. The organic standards can be certainly gaining the thrust of organic farming as expressed by the 34 respondents.

Flip Side of the Marketing Practices Associated with Organic Farm Products

Farm products are being marketed in the country in a way that is not exactly customer-friendly. Hence the study invited the respondents to expose the flip side of the marketing practices accompanying with organic farm products in the country. The expressions of the respondents are presented in the table-3.

Table-3 Flip Side of the Marketing Practices Associated with Organic Farm Products

Flip side aspects	Number of Respondents
Customer-friendly labelling is amiss	47
No logo distinguishes organic products from non-organic products	47
Accreditation that establishes the “organic” content and nature of the product is not carried by the product	46
The prefix “organic” attracts a premium and hence some marketers and organic farmers game the system	46
The organics market is still a niche market	45
Under the umbrella of organic products, some non-organic products are also marketed	44

Form the table-3 it is very clear that, 47 respondents are agreed that, the labeling customer-friendly is incorrect, 47 respondents are accepted that the logo which is not helping distinguishing the products as organic and non-organic. The 46 respondents are expressed that, the accreditation the nature of the product never carry the content of organic and which attracts the marketers and farmers in the market systems respectively. 45 respondents are agreed that organic market is functioning still as a niche market as well as 44 respondents are expressed that under the umbrella system a few of the non-organic products are marketing in the name of organic products.

Implications of the New Organic Standards Mandated by the Regulator

On January 1, 2019, the government mandated clear and legible consumer-friendly labelling for organic products. Hence the study pursued to recognize the inferences of the obligation for the stakeholders associated with the organics industry. Their accounts to the inquiry give the impression in the following Table-4.

Table-4 Implications of The New Organic Standards Mandated by the Regulator

Implications	Number of respondents
Exempting organic food marketed directly to end-users by small producers strikes a discordant note	46
Transparent labelling will help rope in more farmers and more customers	43
Customer base will widen	33
Organic farming will gain momentum	31
Export of organic products to markets like US will improve	29

From the table-4 it can be presented that, 46 respondents are expressed that small producers may conflict if there is any exemption of organic food sold to the ultimate users. The transparent labeling can be useful to the end-users and farmers as responded by 43 respondents. The base of the customers can be broadened and momentum can be gained by the organic farming as replied by 33 and 31 respondents respectively. 29 respondents are answered that the export of organic products may enhance as in the United States economy.

The following Table Reveals the Computation of Chi Square Test

Category	Observed Values		
	Yes	No	Total
Organic farmers	41	9	50
Consultant	44	6	50
Total	85	15	100
Category	Expected Values		
	Yes	No	Total
Organic farmers	42.5	7.5	50
Consultant	42.5	7.5	50
Total	85	15	100
	Yes	No	
o-e	-1.5000	1.5000	
	1.5000	-1.5000	
(o-e) ²	2.2500	2.2500	
	2.2500	2.2500	
((o-e) ²)/e	0.0529	0.3000	

	0.0529	0.3000	
CV	0.1059	0.6000	0.7059
TV			3.8415
p			0.9506

The calculated value of Chi-square is 0.7059, which is less than the table value of 3.8415 for an alpha of 0.05 at 1 degree of freedom. Henceforward the null hypothesis is accepted that, under the umbrella of organic products, some non-organic products are also marketed.

Summary of Findings

1. Accreditation that establishes the “organic” content and nature of the product is not carried by the product over 43 respondents. Under the umbrella of organic products, some non-organic products are also marketed, claim 41 respondents. The prefix “organic” attracts a premium and hence some marketers and organic farmers game the system, allege 39 respondents.
2. Transparent labelling will help rope in more farmers and more customers, aver 40 respondents. Customer base will widen over 38 respondents. Export of organic products to markets like US will improve over 38 respondents. Organic farming will gain momentum, state 34 respondents.
3. Customer-friendly labelling is amiss, cite 47 respondents. No logo distinguishes organic products from non-organic products, cite 47 respondents. The prefix “organic” attracts a premium and hence some marketers and organic farmers game the system, argue 46 respondents. The organics market is still a niche market, remind 45 respondents. Under the umbrella of organic products, some non-organic products are also marketed, maintain 44 respondents.
4. Exempting organic food marketed directly to end-users by small producers strikes a discordant note, over 46 respondents. Transparent labelling will help rope in more farmers and more customers, assert 43 respondents. Customer base will widen, insist 33 respondents. Organic farming will gain momentum, remind 31 respondents. Export of organic products to markets like US will improve, maintain 29 respondents.

Conclusions

Under the umbrella of organic products, some non-organic products are also marketed to this day although such instances have been coming down upon introduction of the labelling requirements. The law should ensure that such instances do not repeat through strict enforcement of the requirements. Transparent labelling will help rope more farmers and more customers into the industry since the credibility of organic products will rise. Export of organic products to US, a major market for organics, will rise. Presently, Indian exporters are not in the good books of US importers, no thanks to some unscrupulous Indian exporters who had exported fake organic products and thus queered the pitch for scrupulous Indian exporters. The organics market is still a niche market. In course of time, with sales volumes picking up and pricing becoming customer-friendly, more and more people are likely to gravitate towards the organics market. Eventually, it may become a mainstream or mass market. Exempting organic food marketed directly to end-users by small producers strikes a discordant note, to say the least. It will lead the other producers to masquerade as small producers and engage in exploiting by the system.

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